

THE FUTURE OF MULTI-CULTURAL SOCIETIES

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Abstract: In a global World, many of our cities and larger urban areas are in reality the true picture of a 21st century multicultural society. International cities like Amsterdam, Berlin, London, Moscow, New York, Shanghai and Singapore are the face of the new global societies we live in. How will our perceptions on multi-cultural societies change in this next decade? People naturally move to seek a better life; this occurred in the 19th and 20th century America, and Europe, but also on a local scale within countries, as our urban centers expanded. This movement also shaped our perceptions on what a multi cultural society looked and felt like. New York is a good example, where the majority of migrants did mix, adopt the culture but in some cases formed their own mono-cultural areas- which we still consider today -"multi-cultural."

Keyword: *Multi-Cultural; Societies; Education; Identity; diversity;*

Introduction

In the 21st century many of our multi cultural cities are patchworks of a mono cultural world, as migrants prefer to live within their own communities, and often bring their own customs with them. This has forced us to look at the real meaning of multi-culture, and evaluate how a successful this type of society should be viewed. The acceptance of the local language and a marriage between members of both cultures are two essential ingredients of a multi-ethnic society. The fusion of the food we eat, and the clothes we wear also should be considered another ingredient to create a successful melting pot.

Economic change and welfare reforms are making many people who live in these urban areas question whether this really works, when in some cases new migrants and local people live apart from each other. This has divided Berlin, London and Paris, which all face pressure to rethink what really are the true aspects of a multi-cultural society?

What is the future of Multi-Cultural Societies?

The most successful people have actually embraced the idea of a global society. A surprisingly wide range of business & political leaders are married to a partner from a different country, speak several languages, and are at home in several cultures. The least successful people are often mono-culturally minded, and prefer to stay in their own communities, whilst failing to accept other cultural influences. This reality is the borderline between a successful society, and one that becomes angry, divisive and discontent.

Multi-cultural societies do work in a global economy, but the perception of a 21st century society that embraces this ideal, should take in the account of encouraging the blending of all cultures into one melting pot. The future of a multi-cultural society could be seen in the streets of our international cities in the future, and many people are watching how austerity measures will affect the cities of Berlin, London, and New York.

Discussion

A. Building a Creative World in a Multi-Cultural Society

The practice of visual art in most multi-cultural societies especially in Africa is often approached in multi-dimensional ways. Although art itself knows no boundary, the culture as well as the artist's environment continues to play an influential role in kind or type of art that the artist creates. Take Nigeria for example, there are approximately (or over) five hundred ethnic groups which the Berlin conference carved under one geographical area. The living and co-existing together of the peoples within the boundary has over the years been sustained by the cultural understanding of the individual groups. These groups have as well as practice varying cultures which is exhibited in their different forms of art.

While at some instances, cultural events are used as avenues for preaching the peace and unity of the nation (Nigeria), it is difficult to say that these cultures have a harmonizing point where each social or ethnic group in Nigeria feels at peace. For example, when a Yoruba man sees a Nok terra-cotta peace, he immediately links it to the cultures people in the Northern part of Nigeria. He tends to have an alienated way of

embracing it. On the other hand, an Ife naturalistic portrait makes him (the Yoruba) feels more homely. Also, if an Ibo man sees a painting of Fulani milk maids, he feels the same way, but embraces his Igbo-Ukwu pieces. All of them (Ibo, Yoruba, Hausa, and other smaller ethnic groups) do not express this out-rightly, rather, it more like a feeling unexpressed but deduced from the knowledge of the person on such artifact.

The network of museums in Nigeria managed by National Council for Museums and Monuments (NCMM) have tried to create cultural harmony among the different socio-cultural groups in Nigeria by providing opportunity for the display of various cultural product, yet the public have not really been educated to patronize them as desired. The visual art sector, on the other hand, artists have not been able to adequately creative a visual culture using a central cultural symbol which all Nigerian ethnic group will feel at home with. The unifying symbols which all ethnic or social groups look up to is the national flag and the court of arm. The Society of Nigerian Artists (SNA) which is the apex professional body covering all practicing artists in Nigeria decides to adopt the Benin mask stolen during the British punitive expedition, as its ideal logo. This could be seen a political statement against the unwholesome shipping of valuable cultural materials which took place in the pre/colonial periods by the Europeans.

B. Multi-Cultural Society and Education

Over half a million protestors against the proposed immigration bill in California has again marked out the fact, how many new people are coming to America every year to realize 'The Great American Dream' and secondly it raises few questions about, how we will assimilate them in our society. Culturally diverse societies are living in America with relative harmony toward each other. This harmony is not the result of assimilation of these diverse communities into the dominant culture but by progressive respects toward each other.

C. Education in Multi Cultural Society

Education has played major role in the emergence of United States as dominant power in World War II. Our education system focused on progressive values and liberalism, which led to the advancements in science and technology. Post 9/11 what we are witnessing is a growing intolerance towards different religions and cultures, which is disturbing the harmony in American society. Today the challenge in front of our education system is two fold - understanding cultural and religious sensitivities and inculcating them in our daily living. Keeping the above objectives in mind, I have put forward few recommendations that will help in going ahead with our educational system in grow cultural diversity.

Understanding the history, background and other cultural differences will improve the understanding among students of various cultures in the school. It will help building an atmosphere where students across the table will be much more receptive in understanding each others view points. Cross cultural education system will help in eradicating uneasy and confronting situations like the 'Prophet Pictures'. In our modern society the head on approach won't bring harmony but instead it will splurge situations where more and more people will feel uncomfortable in each others company. This uneasiness will stem from one fear of how the other will react to what one says and secondly people will notice more difference among each other than the similarities.

Today we have huge inequalities with in our society sort of which we have witnessed during and aftermath of hurricane Katrina. These inequalities may be due to economic differences or due to educational differences. Sensitization towards these inequalities is a step forward in right direction and I personally believe that the recommendations will achieve in making students across America to understand these differences. Further understanding these inequalities will help us in developing an educational system that works to remove them and groom more prepared and sensitive students in the future.

D. Assimilation or Multi-culturalism

Maybe we need a combination of the two.

What does it mean to be American? Does it mean everyone talks the same and looks the same and believes the same things? Does it mean forgetting everything that our parents and grandparents had to go through to get to this country? Does it mean forgetting all the customs and foods and stories they were raised with? Wouldn't that be awfully hard to do? And wouldn't this be a boring place to live?

This country was a huge land with very few inhabitants and then people from all parts of the world left their own homes and troubles and came here with one goal: to make a better life for their families than they could have in their homeland. They were the entrepreneurs, the hard working, stubborn, brave people who came with nothing and made something of themselves. In the process they built a great country for us.

George Washington said in 1783 that our borders were open for the wealthy and educated and oppressed and persecuted of all nations and religions, who were free to participate in all our rights and privileges - if these newcomers followed American standards of decency and proper conduct. He wanted them to assimilate to their new country's values. And most of them did. Most of these European immigrants considered themselves Americans and never saw their homelands or families again. This was mainly because travel to Europe was difficult, not because the new country insisted on it, although it made assimilation easier to accomplish.

The goal used to be for all immigrants of different backgrounds to "melt" into a new race of people. During the civil rights movement of the 1960s, this ideal was challenged when we were encouraged to celebrate diversity and move beyond this melting pot. Assimilation was changed to multi-culturalism.

Multi-culturalism is promoted by many, but it doesn't give the people a common goal, belief or even language anymore. Many of the immigrants here now have no knowledge of the history of this country and no interest in learning it. They have no loyalty to any common idea or belief, and often don't consider themselves

Americans. A large number never learn English and never learn their rights or responsibilities and never become a part of this country. What can we do to help them become Americans?

The task of assimilating into a new culture doesn't rest with the people already there, it is the responsibility of the immigrants to take advantage of the opportunities that are offered to them in their new home. They must try to adapt to life in this country. It doesn't mean they should forget their own customs, it doesn't mean they should change entirely, but it does mean they should do their best to learn the language and the rules.

When Americans look back at their history of immigration, they assume that assimilation is a relatively easy process, since their parents and grandparents did it. But it is very hard for immigrants to give up old languages, customs and practices so they can be absorbed into their new society. Most people possess a strong, passionate attachment to their own culture and way of life and in most cases, they are emigrating because of poverty in their own country. If their country offered them a good life for their families, most of them would stay home.

We need the immigrants who are here and will need more all the time. We should find a way to combine the assimilation we used to strive for and the multiculturalism that so many want now. We have to convince these new people to become Americans without giving up all of the customs from their former homes.

Conclusion

Today, even in the study of Nigerian art, the curriculum treats modern Nigerian art in a lump-some manner with great biases to individual cultures like Yoruba, Ibo or Ibibio art/cultures. Yet the cultural background of artists from these ethnic groups continues to manifest in their individual art works. On the other hand, the Nok, Ife, or Benin art pieces are treated as mere art traditions which formed the rudimentary clue to the study of art history in Nigeria.

So far, many artists have lost the desire to build a creative world that will inevitably unite the different cultural groups using symbols that all Nigerian groups will

embrace as theirs. The few Nigerian artists that seem to be leading in the field of visual art practice and which could initiate a course in order to achieve this quest are obviously looking in other directions. At the moment, the visual art sector is still a platform for exhibiting cultural in diversity. This means that Nigerians in groups; not Nigeria as one.

The recommendation of increasing diversity among classes across America is especially a worthy one. Today we saw how schools are either neighborhood centered or race centered. Increasing diversity will bring different perspective in the same class and students from the very early age will able to know that each individual has a different way of tackling the same situation.

I think this understanding of being different and recognizing it as it is will bring forth a new revolution in our education system. This very understanding will reduce the 'Them vs Us' situation in our community, society and in this world. It will build a world where cultural differences as well as similarities will exist, without assigning values, i.e., better or worse, right or wrong, to those cultural differences and variation.

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